

The Role of Biocrust Cyanobacteria on Seedling Emergence in Soil Substrates Used in Ecosystem Restoration

Running head: Cyanobacteria Bio-priming for Ecosystem Restoration

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This thesis was formatted according to the style of

Restoration Ecology

8209 words

This thesis is submitted in partial fulfilment for a

Bachelor of Science (Honours)

BIOL5442-5445 Research Dissertation

School of Biological Sciences

Faculty of Science

The University of Western Australia

(October 2018)

1 **Bio-priming seeds with cyanobacteria: effects on germination, recruitment**
2 **and growth of native plants and soil function**

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16 **Title**

17 Bio-priming seeds with cyanobacteria: effects on germination, recruitment and growth of native
18 plants and soil function

19 **Running head**

20 Bio-priming seeds with cyanobacteria

21 **Abstract**

22 Cyanobacteria are photosynthetic bacteria that form a fundamental part of soil biocrusts,
23 enhance soil function and structure, and can promote plant growth. We assessed the potential
24 of cyanobacteria as a seed bio-primer for mine-site restoration in an arid region in Western
25 Australia, examining its effects on native plant growth and the characteristics of mine soil
26 substrates used in dryland restoration. Cyanobacteria strains indigenous to the study region
27 (*Microcoleus* sp., *Nostoc* sp. *Scytonema* sp. and *Leptolyngbya* sp.) were used to create an
28 inoculant. Seeds of seven native plant species were bio-primed with the inoculant, and their
29 germination and growth assessed in a laboratory experiment. Seedling growth after bio-priming
30 was assessed in a glasshouse experiment for a subset of three species, in two different substrates
31 (topsoil and mine waste). Soil properties related to soil function, e.g. total organic carbon, total
32 nitrogen and microbial activity were also measured. Minor effects on germination were
33 recorded with only significantly higher germination rates reported in *E. gamophylla* and soil
34 parameters were generally higher in topsoil than in mine waste, regardless of bio-priming
35 treatment. However, bio-priming resulted in seedlings of four species producing longer radicles
36 and/or shoots. For example, seedling root lengths of bio-primed *G. wickhamii* were 57% larger
37 than the control treatment (30.1 ± 4.3 and 13.0 ± 1.6 mm respectively); and shoots of *T. wiseana*
38 were 54% longer in the bio-primed treatment (18.6 ± 1.6 mm) compared to the control
39 (8.53 ± 1.4 mm). Overall, our results highlight that bio-priming with cyanobacteria may improve
40 plant growth for some species commonly used in dryland restoration.

41 **Keywords:** Indigenous cyanobacteria; Land degradation; Biocrust; Mine rehabilitation; Seed
42 coating; Soil microbial activity

43 **Author Contributions**

44 MC, MMR, TE, DM conceived and designed the research; MC, MMR, MO, AC performed the
45 experiments; MC, MMR, MO, AC analyzed the data; MC, MMR, TE, MO, AC, DM wrote and
46 edited the manuscript.

47 **Implications for practice:**

- 48 - Bio-priming native plant seeds with indigenous cyanobacteria from biocrust can promote
49 seedling growth of arid species used in dryland restoration
- 50 - Cyanobacteria inoculants for seed bio-priming should be tested using different
51 cyanobacteria genera and consortiums as these may have species-specific differences in
52 plant responses
- 53 - Implementation of this technology in large-scale restoration will require further research on
54 targeted delivery of cyanobacteria bio-priming inoculants

55 **Introduction**

56 Land degradation is an environmental problem affecting almost a quarter of the global
57 terrestrial surface (Stavi & Lal 2015). In Australia, approximately half of all forest land has
58 been cleared or severely modified, and other areas of vegetation and soils are at risk of
59 degradation by a range of threats, including by industrial activities such as mining (Deo, 2011;
60 Bradshaw 2012). Dryland regions are particularly affected by land degradation processes
61 (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005), and have overwhelmingly low rates of restoration
62 success (James et al. 2013).

63 In the Australian arid zone, poor restoration success has been attributed to unfavourable
64 climatic conditions (Lewandrowski et al. 2017), low content of soil organic matter and nutrients
65 in substrates used for restoration (Merino-Martín et al. 2017; Kneller et al. 2018), and naturally
66 high seedling mortality rates. In the context of mine restoration, topsoil, which is commonly
67 stockpiled and subsequently spread in the targeted restoration areas, is crucial to support the
68 establishment of native plant species (Muñoz-Rojas et al. 2016). Topsoil contains seeds, soil
69 organic matter, nutrients, and microbial communities (Golos et al. 2016; Birnbaum et al. 2017)
70 and its use in restoration can be beneficial if managed effectively (Erickson et al. 2017).

71 In large-scale restoration there may be a limited availability of topsoil (Kneller et al. 2018),
72 meaning nutrient-deficient waste materials produced during mining operations become an
73 alternative growth media (Muñoz-Rojas et al. 2016; Bateman et al. 2018). A shortage of topsoil
74 also necessitates the direct return of seeds to the restoration site, however, successful
75 recruitment from seed provides its own challenges in these environments. To address the often
76 poor recruitment of sown seeds, recent research has focussed on enhancement technologies,
77 including seed coating and pelleting, to facilitate mechanical dispersal (Madsen et al. 2016;
78 Pedrini et al. 2017). Seed coatings can also incorporate bio-active symbiotic organisms, such

79 as soil microorganisms, to protect these from external factors and provide an effective site-
80 delivery mechanism (O'Callaghan, 2016).

81 Recent studies have shown the potential role of cyanobacteria, naturally occurring bacteria in
82 biological crusts (hereafter “biocrusts”), to promote plant growth and increase fertility of
83 degraded soils in dryland restoration (Bowker et al. 2007; Ferrenberg et al. 2017; Roman et al.
84 2018). Cyanobacteria are primary components of biocrusts, a community of macro- and micro-
85 organisms found in the upper surface of soils (Büdel et al. 2016; Chilton et al. 2017), and
86 consist of a variety of species with different morphologies and adaptations that allow them to
87 facilitate key regulating processes in the soil (Antoninka et al. 2016). These photosynthetic
88 bacteria can survive extreme environmental conditions such as high temperatures, extreme pH,
89 and desiccation (Singh et al. 2016). Despite several studies supporting cyanobacteria
90 application in dryland restoration (Bowker, 2007; Chamizo et al. 2018), there are contrasting
91 opinions on the effects of these organisms on germination and growth of vascular plants (Song
92 et al. 2017; Havrilla and Barger, 2018; Havrilla et al. 2019)

93 Cyanobacteria have been found to secrete growth-promoting substances e.g. auxins, cytokinins
94 and gibberellins in their EPS (Chamizo et al. 2018). These chemicals have important functions
95 in plant growth regulation, metabolism and development (Hashtroudi et al. 2013). For example
96 cytokinins have been considered as growth-promoting substances enhancing seed germination,
97 shoot length and grain weight, amongst other aspects of plant growth (Mazhar et al. 2013).
98 Recent studies have shown the positive effect of bio-priming seeds with cyanobacteria on
99 germination and seedling growth of native plants (Muñoz-Rojas et al. 2018a). Soaking the
100 seeds in a cyanobacterial suspension allows the imbibition into the seed and creates ideal
101 conditions for their inoculation and colonization in the seed (Mahmood et al. 2016). In addition,
102 the application of beneficial microbes such as cyanobacteria to seeds, can be an efficient tool
103 for targeted delivery of the inoculum into the soil following germination (O'Callaghan, 2016).
104 However, the ability of the cyanobacteria inoculants applied as seed treatments in native plants
105 to multiply and colonise the root and the surrounding soil, has not yet been investigated.

106 In this study we set out to assess the potential of bio-priming seeds of native plants with
107 cyanobacteria for enhancing seed and seedling performance in dryland restoration. We selected
108 seven plant species important to restoration in Pilbara region of Western Australia (*Acacia*
109 *hilliana*, *Acacia inaequilatera*, *Eucalyptus gamophylla*, *Grevillea wickhamii*, *Indigofera*
110 *monophylla*, *Senna notabilis* and *Triodia wiseana*) and determined the effects of seed bio-

111 priming with an inoculant of indigenous cyanobacteria on (i) seed germination and seedling
112 recruitment (successful establishment) and growth in two soil substrates and (ii) soil properties
113 of the rhizosphere, e.g. soil organic carbon, nitrogen content, and microbial activity.

114 We hypothesised that seed bio-priming with a cyanobacteria consortium inoculum would not
115 have an inhibitory effect on the native plant species and would enhance seedling growth and
116 establishment of most of them. The bio-priming application was also expected to transfer
117 cyanobacteria inoculum from the seed to the spermosphere and rhizosphere to promote an
118 increase in soil organic carbon, total nitrogen and microbial activity.

119 **Methods**

120 ***Cyanobacteria strains and culturing***

121 Cyanobacterial strains of four species (*Leptolyngbya* sp. *Microcoleus* sp. *Nostoc* sp. and
122 *Scytonema* sp. Table S1) from biocrusts sampled at Gallery Hill, Pilbara Region, Western
123 Australia, were isolated and characterised as previously described (Muñoz-Rojas et al. 2018a).
124 Cultures were grown in BG-11 media (Cyanobacteria BG-11 Freshwater Solution, Merck)
125 under light: dark cycles (16:8h at 28/20°C) and constant light conditions (80 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$) in a
126 plant growth chamber (Thermoline Scientific Climatron 2400-TH-CO₂) at the School of
127 Biological, Earth and Environmental Sciences (UNSW, Sydney).

128 ***Seed preparation and cyanobacteria bio-priming of seeds***

129 Seeds previously collected from wild plant populations in the Pilbara in November - December
130 2013 and stored in a controlled environment room at 15°C and 15% relative humidity, were
131 used in this study. Prior to use in experiments, any potentially non-viable seeds were identified
132 via x-ray analysis (Faxitron MX-20) or microscopy and removed to exclude seed quality as a
133 factor contributing to the germination response to bio-priming. The seven selected plant species
134 (Table S1) belong to a variety of families commonly found in the Pilbara and used in mine
135 restoration (Erickson et al. 2016; Bateman et al. 2018). Seeds were pre-treated according to
136 dormancy type (Table S1). All seeds were then sterilised in 1% (w/v) calcium hypochlorite
137 solution for 30 min and rinsed, prior to cyanobacteria bio-priming.

138 To create the cyanobacteria bio-priming inoculant, equal biomass proportions of *Leptolyngbya*
139 sp. *Microcoleus* sp. *Nostoc* sp. and *Scytonema* sp. were used. Cultures were filtered and
140 resuspended in milli-Q water to achieve a concentration of 1g/L. Chlorophyll a and carotenoid
141 contents for each cyanobacteria culture were analysed at the exponential growth phase as in
142 (Zavřel et al. 2015) (Table S2) before composing the inoculant. Biomass concentrations for

143 each strain were determined based on the dry weight obtained after filtering and drying in an
144 oven at 60°C for 2 h. Seeds were placed in separate beakers for each species and treatment
145 combination, before being bio-primed with the inoculant (1g/L) or in milli-Q water (as the
146 control). Beakers were then agitated on an orbital shaker (Ratek EOM5) for 30 h at a low speed
147 at 25°C. After agitation, seeds were directly transferred to Petri dishes for the seed germination
148 experiment or to the mesocosms for the plant recruitment and growth experiment.

149 ***Seed germination and early seedling growth***

150 Bio-primed and non-primed seeds (n=100) of all seven species were plated in 90 mm Petri
151 dishes on filter paper (n = 4 P dishes per treatment; 25 seeds per dish) and incubated under a
152 16/8 h alternating temperature (28/20°C) and light:dark cycle in the laboratory. Each dish was
153 initially irrigated with 2 ml milli-Q water and later topped up with another 2 ml to prevent
154 drying out. Germination was scored as emergence of radicle and recorded daily for 16 d. Data
155 was reported as the proportion of viable seeds that germinated. Early seedling growth was
156 determined by measuring shoot and radicle lengths of 10-day old seedlings, recorded for up to
157 32 randomly chosen seedlings per treatment.

158 ***Plant recruitment and growth***

159 Cultures of the selected cyanobacteria strains were transported to Kings Park and Botanic
160 Garden (Perth, Western Australia) in sealed 50 ml falcon tubes and the bio-priming inocula
161 was composed as per the laboratory germination experiment. A multi-factorial mesocosm
162 experiment was established and included two seed treatments, namely seeds primed with water
163 (control) and seeds bio-primed (as above) with the cyanobacteria inoculant, and two soil
164 substrates planted out with a 3-species subset of the original seven species: *A. hilliana*, *G.*
165 *wickhamii* and *T. wiseana*. Soil substrates were collected from an active mine site located in
166 the southern region of the Pilbara and included previously stockpiled topsoil (TS) and mine
167 waste soil (WS), both commonly used in mine restoration (Bateman et al. 2018; Kneller et al.
168 2018). The experiment was conducted over five months (July – December 2018) in a glasshouse
169 facility at The University of Western Australia (UWA).

170 In order to control for water availability, all mesocosms were maintained at 30°C (a temperature
171 that mimics environmental conditions during the rainfall season in the Pilbara) and watered
172 daily to maintain field capacity throughout the study. Mesocosms consisted of heavy-duty
173 storages containers (590W x 390D x 260H mm) with a volume of 44 L. Holes (4 mm) were
174 drilled in the bottom of the containers to allow drainage before they were filled 200 mm deep

175 with either TS or WS (n = 4 per treatment). Each container was sown with 40 *A. hilliana*, 100
176 *G. wickhamii* and 100 *T. wiseana* seeds to form a representative Pilbara plant community
177 assemblage (Erickson et al. 2016). Two additional blank containers for each soil treatment that
178 did not have sown seeds were included. The 18 mesocosms were placed in the glasshouse in a
179 randomised order to prevent placement bias, and subjected to reticulation of 0.8 L daily
180 (irrigated in two intervals of two minutes) to simulate rainfall in the Pilbara (Muñoz-Rojas et
181 al. 2018b). Seedling emergence was scored daily for four weeks and every week thereafter.
182 Shoot length was measured from the surface of the soil and recorded five, six, eight and 20
183 weeks after seeds were sown. Plant biomass was also measured after 20 weeks (completion of
184 the experiment).

185 ***Measurement of soil function parameters***

186 Soil samples (at least 500 g) were collected before (TS Before, WS Before) and at the end of
187 the experiment (TS Bio-primed, TS Control, WS Bio-primed and WS Control) from all
188 containers to measure soil indicators related to fertility and function, including soil C, N
189 contents, C:N and microbial activity (Muñoz-Rojas, 2018). Samples were dried at 40°C over
190 72 h, sieved at 2 mm and stored at 25°C prior to measurements. Two subsamples were taken
191 from each sample to determine Total Organic Carbon (TOC) and Total Nitrogen (TN) content,
192 and microbial activity, respectively. TOC and TN content were analysed using the DUMAS
193 total combustion technique with the vario-MACRO CNS (Elementar, USA) (Buckee,
194 1994). The 1-day CO₂ burst (Solvita) test was used to measure soil microbial activity (CO₂-C
195 ppm) based on the burst of CO₂ produced after the dried soil has been rewetted and incubated
196 at 25°C for 24 h (Kneller et al. 2018).

197 ***Data Analysis***

198 All statistical analyses were conducted using the R statistical platform Version 3.1.2 (R Core
199 Team, 2017). To assess germination for the laboratory experiment, species were analysed
200 separately to compare between inoculated and control seeds. Total proportion of seeds
201 germinated at the end of 16 days was calculated and analysed using a binomial Generalised
202 Linear Model (GLM). Germination rate was plotted using cumulative germination over time
203 and analysed using the dose-response models (DRM) in the RStudio drc package (time to 50%
204 germination (T50) used to compare rates). For analysing shoot and radicle lengths, we used a
205 single factor ANOVA.

206 For the mesocosms experiment using different soil substrates, plant traits (shoot and radicle
207 lengths and plant biomass) were analysed for each species separately using a two-factor
208 ANOVA, with treatment (inoculated vs control) and substrate (TS vs WS) as the predictors.
209 Differences in soil function parameters (TOC, TN, C:N and microbial activity) were similarly
210 analysed using a two-factor ANOVA. Comparisons between means were performed with the
211 Tukey's HSD test ($P < 0.05$). All data were tested for normality and variance homogeneity
212 using the Shapiro–Wilk and Levene's tests prior to analysis.

213 **Results**

214 ***Seed germination and early seedling growth***

215 Total germination of each species did not differ significantly between treatments. However,
216 bio-primed seeds of *E. gamophylla* had a significantly faster germination rate (0.90 ± 0.045)
217 compared to the non-primed control seeds (0.81 ± 0.06) ($P < 0.001$), whereas bio-primed *G.*
218 *wickhamii* seeds had slower germination (0.16 ± 0.02) than the non-primed (0.34 ± 0.05) ($P <$
219 0.001) (Figure 1). For seeds of all other species, the germination rate of non-primed and bio-
220 primed seeds was not significantly different (Figure 1).

221 Bio-primed seeds produced seedlings with longer shoot and radicle lengths for several species
222 ($P < 0.05$, Figure 2), compared with non-primed seeds. The bio-primed seeds of *E. gamophylla*,
223 *G. wickhamii* and *T. wiseana* produced both longer shoots and radicles, while bio-primed seeds
224 of *Acacia hilliana* and *S. notabilis* produced seedlings with significantly longer radicles ($P <$
225 0.05 , Figure 2). Larger effects overall were observed in *G. wickhamii* and *T. wiseana*. For
226 example, seedling root lengths of bio-primed *G. wickhamii* were 57% larger than the control
227 treatment (30.1 ± 4.3 and 13.0 ± 1.6 mm respectively); and shoots of *T. wiseana* were 54% longer
228 in the bio-primed treatment (18.6 ± 1.6 mm) compared to the control (8.53 ± 1.4 mm). No
229 significant differences in the shoot and radicle lengths were found between treatments for the
230 other species.

231 232 ***Plant recruitment and growth and soil function parameters***

233 The proportion of emerged seedlings for *A. hilliana* ranged between 0.42 and 0.57 across all
234 treatments and soil substrates, and significantly higher emergence was recorded in bio-primed
235 seeds sown in WS substrate (0.57 ± 0.05 ; $P < 0.001$), compared to the TS. For *G. wickhamii*,
236 seedling emergence ranged between 0.08 and 0.13 across all treatment and substrate
237 combinations, and for *T. wiseana* from 0.19 to 0.41, with significantly higher emergence of

238 bio-primed seeds in TS compared to bio-primed seeds in WS ($P < 0.001$). Differences in
239 seedling emergence between bio-primed and non-primed (control) treatments within TS or
240 within WS were not significant for any of the plant species (Figure 3).

241 Shoot lengths of *A. hilliana* after 20 weeks of growth were significantly higher ($P < 0.01$) in
242 the bio-primed seeds for both substrates (100.0 ± 13.8 mm and 72.9 ± 5.4 mm in TS and WS,
243 respectively), compared to the control treatments (72.8 ± 6.6 and 55.4 ± 3.2 mm) (Table 1). Plant
244 biomass for *A. hilliana* was also significantly larger in the WS bio-primed treatment compared
245 to WS un-primed ($P < 0.01$, Table 1). Shoot lengths of *T. wiseana* seedlings were significantly
246 larger for the bio-primed seeds grown in the TS (179.0 ± 5.2 mm), compared to the un-primed
247 seeds (138.3 ± 9.4 mm) (Table 1). Shoot lengths of *Grevillea wickhamii* were similar between
248 control and bio-primed for both TS and WS after 20 weeks.

249 Soil properties (e.g. TOC and TN) were generally significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) in the TS
250 compared to the WS (Figure 4), regardless of the seed priming treatment. In the TS, TOC
251 ranged between 1.14 and 1.26 (%) and TN between 0.026 and 0.038 %. In the WS, TOC and
252 TN values were lower than 0.02 % and 0.002%, respectively. Similarly, soil microbial activity
253 was not significantly different between bio-primed WS (3.2 ± 0.3 CO₂-C ppm) and TS (3.3 ± 0.2
254 CO₂-C ppm) treatments.

255 **Discussion**

256 Our results provide evidence that bio-priming seeds with indigenous cyanobacteria did not have
257 an inhibitory effect on the germination of any of the studied plant species and promoted the
258 early seedling growth of most species. Although there was only minor effects on germination,
259 bio-priming seeds with cyanobacteria in the laboratory experiment resulted in seedlings with
260 longer shoots in three species (*E. gamophylla*, *G. wickhamii*, and *T. wiseana*), and seedlings
261 with longer radicles in four species (*E. gamophylla*, *G. wickhamii*, *T. wiseana*, *S. notabilis* and,
262 *A. hilliana*). Other studied species of the family Fabaceae such as *I. monophylla* and *A.*
263 *inaequilatera* appeared to be less responsive to the cyanobacteria bio-priming at this early life
264 stage. These plant species are known to form symbiotic relationships with rhizobia (N-fixing
265 bacteria) as an adaptation to N deficient soils (Remigi et al. 2016; Tedersoo et al. 2018), with
266 some even capable of using atmospheric N through the association with these bacteria, located
267 within their root nodules (Oldroyd & Dixon, 2014). This may be a contributing factor to the
268 limited effect of bio-priming with N-fixing cyanobacteria observed in this study, and that of

269 Muñoz-Rojas et al. (2018a); with such an alternate N source, these species are not limited to
270 harnessing N from the soil.

271 In Muñoz-Rojas et al. (2018a), the effects of bio-priming seeds of a range of species native to
272 the Pilbara, including some in the present study (*A. hilliana*, *G. wickhamii*, *S. notabilis*, *T.*
273 *epactia* and *T. wiseana*), were tested, although with a different bio-priming inoculant composed
274 of equal proportions of the cyanobacteria species *Microcoleus paludosus* and *Nostoc*
275 *microscopicum* (Muñoz-Rojas et al. 2018a). Overall, other than for the germination of *G.*
276 *wickhamii* seeds, both studies reported no inhibitory effect of bio-priming on germination with
277 either of the two different cyanobacteria composites. However, contrary to the results of
278 Muñoz-Rojas et al. (2018a) in which enhanced seedling growth was reported only for *A.*
279 *hilliana*, in the present study we found that bio-priming seeds of *G. wickhamii* and *T. wiseana*
280 resulted in significantly longer shoots and radicles, and significantly longer radicles for *A.*
281 *hilliana* and *S. notabilis*. Thus it appears there exists species-specific responses to the different
282 cyanobacteria strains and their proportions used in the bio-priming inoculant. The present study
283 used two additional cyanobacteria strains, *Leptolyngbya sp.* and *Scytonema sp.* to create the
284 bio-priming inoculant. Despite belonging to the same order as *Nostoc sp.*, *Scytonema sp.* is
285 morphologically different and has been found to be better adapted to warm temperatures than
286 *Nostoc sp.* remaining viable at higher temperatures (Muñoz-Martín et al. 2018). *Leptolyngbya*
287 encompasses a diverse group of filamentous cyanobacteria with some capable of resurrecting
288 after desiccation (Shimura et al. 2015). A specific *Leptolyngbya* species, *Leptolyngbya ohadii*,
289 was found to produce compositionally complex exopolymeric substances (EPS) and form
290 biocrust that aggregates sand, chelate nutrients and maintain hydration in the absence of
291 nutrients (Mugnai et al. 2018). In order to understand the specific effects each cyanobacteria
292 strain has on the recruitment of native plant species; more targeted experiments should be
293 conducted. With advancement in bioinformatic approaches, active biological and chemical
294 compounds in EPS of each strain could be analysed in order to determine specific metabolites
295 promoting particular aspects of plant development (Swenson et al. 2018).

296 Soil properties analysed in this study, which are linked to soil quality and function in ecosystem
297 restoration (Muñoz-Rojas, 2018) were found to differ greatly between TS and WS, while
298 minimal differences were found in these parameters between soils sown with bio-primed or un-
299 primed seeds. Studies involving the formation of cyanobacteria biocrust that have been
300 conducted for a longer period and with varying concentrations of cyanobacteria (Park et al.
301 2017; Muñoz-Rojas et al. 2018b) have provided evidence of other beneficial effects of

302 cyanobacteria addition. For example, Park et al. (2017) applied cyanobacteria at 10 g of dry
303 weight to 4 m² plots over three occasions during a 12-month study to investigate the potential
304 of applying cyanobacteria in combination with other soil-fixing chemicals to combat
305 desertification. In another example, Muñoz-Rojas et al. (2018b) inoculated Petri dishes (0.66
306 m²) of mine waste soil from the Pilbara with cyanobacteria dry weight of 6 g for a three-month
307 study to determine the ability of cyanobacteria to re-colonise mine waste soil. Unlike the
308 present study, Park et al. (2017) and Muñoz-Rojas et al. (2018c) reported biocrust formation
309 and substantial increases in TOC, demonstrating the capability of cyanobacteria to facilitate the
310 enhancement of soil function.

311 In our study, although non-significant, lower levels of TOC and N content were found in TS
312 containing bio-primed seeds, as compared to TS control. This trend may be explained by the
313 competition of cyanobacteria transferred to the rhizosphere with existing microbial
314 communities in the TS, both competing for nutrient resources (Chen et al. 2015). In addition to
315 nutrient resources, these interactions, either competition or facilitation may also depend on soil
316 development and other physicochemical soil properties (Roncero-Ramos et al., 2019). Opposite
317 to the results obtained in the TS, TOC, TN and soil microbial activity were higher in the WS
318 containing bio-primed seeds, compared to the control, although similarly, differences were not
319 significant. Given that there is a slight trend towards increases in these soil parameters, the poor
320 (and not significant) response may be attributed to the short duration of the 20-week experiment
321 and the low cyanobacteria concentration of 1 g/L in a seed bio-priming inoculant, with no
322 follow-up addition to the soil. In the present study we set out to determine the effects of bio-
323 priming of seeds on seed germination, seedling vigour, and soil properties, hence lower
324 concentrations of cyanobacteria were implemented, and no cyanobacteria culture was added
325 directly to the soil.

326 Our results demonstrate that bio-priming native plant seeds with indigenous cyanobacteria from
327 biocrust can promote seedling growth, but additional inoculation of cyanobacteria would be
328 needed to colonize the soil and modify the properties of growth media used in dryland
329 restoration. Alternative soil substrates are often necessary in the restoration of many mine-sites
330 due to a deficit of available topsoil (Bateman et al. 2019). Our results support the use of priming
331 of seeds in cyanobacteria to promote seedling growth of some of the native species, but longer-
332 term trials may be needed to assess the effects on long-term plant survival and soil quality
333 parameters. Despite cyanobacteria bio-priming showing potential as a nutrient supplement to
334 promote artificial cyanobacteria-dominated biocrust (Muñoz-Rojas et al. 2018a), there remain

335 some challenges for implementation in large-scale restoration. Our study has not demonstrated
336 that bio-priming of seeds alone is capable of inducing the effects seen through direct application
337 of cyanobacteria to soil. Based on the positive findings of cyanobacteria applications in
338 multiple fields of research, cyanobacteria could be suitable for seed bio-priming and
339 encapsulation within a polymer seed coat for ecological restoration, but the maintenance of
340 viability of the seed and the cyanobacteria from application through to use in the field is
341 essential. Unlike rhizobia, cyanobacteria can withstand the current conditions of the seed coat
342 due to their resistance to desiccation stress, possibly increasing microbial viability and storage
343 life of coated seeds (Singh et al. 2016).

344 The identification of potential metabolites produced by cyanobacteria that promote seedling
345 recruitment of native plant species is another avenue of research. With recent advancement in
346 bioinformatics and metabolite profiling of cyanobacteria, it may be beneficial to expand on
347 current studies to determine specific growth-promoting metabolites that can easily be produced
348 on a large-scale (Ferrenberg et al. 2017; Swenson et al. 2018).

349 **Acknowledgements**

350 This research was supported by a BHP Western Australia Iron Ore Community Development
351 Project (contract no. 8600048550) under the auspices of the Restoration Seedbank Initiative, a
352 partnership between BHP Western Australia Iron Ore (BHPWAIO), The University of Western
353 Australia and Botanic Gardens and Parks Authority; and the Australian Research Council
354 Discovery Early Career Researcher Award DE180100570.

355 **References** 356

- 357 Antoninka A, Bowker MA, Reed SC, Doherty K (2016) Production of greenhouse-grown
358 biocrust mosses and associated cyanobacteria to rehabilitate dryland soil function.
359 *Restoration Ecology* 24:324-335
- 360 Bateman A, Lewandrowski W, Stevens JC, Muñoz-Rojas M (2018) Ecophysiological
361 indicators to assess drought responses of arid zone native seedlings in reconstructed
362 soils. *Land Degradation & Development* 29:984-993
- 363 Benigno SM, Dixon KW, Stevens JC (2013) Increasing soil water retention with native-sourced
364 mulch improves seedling establishment in postmine Mediterranean sandy soils.
365 *Restoration Ecology* 21:617-626
- 366 Birnbaum C, Bradshaw LE, Ruthrof KX, Fontaine JB (2017) Topsoil stockpiling in restoration:
367 Impact of storage time on plant growth and symbiotic soil biota. *Ecological Restoration*
368 35:237-245
- 369 Bowker MA (2007) Biological soil crust rehabilitation in theory and practice: an underexploited
370 opportunity. *Restoration Ecology* 15:13-23

- 371 Bradshaw CJ (2012) Little left to lose: deforestation and forest degradation in Australia since
372 European colonization. *Journal of Plant Ecology* 5:109-120
- 373 Buckee G 1994. Determination of total nitrogen in barley, malt and beer by Kjeldahl procedures
374 and the Dumas combustion method—collaborative trial. [Journal of the Institute of](#)
375 [Brewing](#) 100:57–64.
- 376 Büdel B, Dulić T, Darienko T, Rybalka N, Friedl T (2016) Cyanobacteria and algae of
377 biological soil crusts. Pages 55-80 In: *Biological Soil Crusts: An Organizing Principle*
378 *in Drylands*. Springer
- 379 Bureau of Meteorology (2018) Newman Aero Monthly Rainfall. Bureau of
380 Meteorology, Australian Government.
381 http://www.bom.gov.au/climate/averages/tables/cw_007176_All.shtml. (Accessed 26
382 Apr 2018)
- 383 Chamizo S, Mugnai G, Rossi FR, Certini G, De Philippis R (2018) Cyanobacteria inoculation
384 improves soil stability and fertility on different textured soils: gaining insights for
385 applicability in soil restoration. *Frontiers in Environmental Science* 6:49
- 386 Chen J, Carrillo Y, Pendall E, Dijkstra FA, Evans RD, Morgan JA, Williams DG (2015) Soil
387 microbes compete strongly with plants for soil inorganic and amino acid nitrogen in a
388 semiarid grassland exposed to elevated CO₂ and warming. *Ecosystems* 18:867-880
- 389 Chilton AM, Neilan BA, and Eldridge DJ (2017) Biocrust morphology is linked to marked
390 differences in microbial community composition. *Plant and Soil* 429:65-75
- 391 Cochrane JA, Hoyle GL, Yates CJ, Wood J, Nicotra AB (2015) Climate warming delays and
392 decreases seedling emergence in a Mediterranean ecosystem. *Oikos* 124:150-160
- 393 Commander LE, Golos PJ, Miller BP, Merritt DJ (2017) Seed germination traits of desert
394 perennials. *Plant ecology* 218:1077-1091
- 395 Erickson T, Barrett R, Merritt D, Dixon K. (2016) *Pilbara seed atlas and field guide: plant*
396 *restoration in Australia's arid northwest*. CSIRO Publishing
- 397 Erickson TE, Muñoz-Rojas M, Kildisheva OA, Stokes BA, White SA, Heyes JL, Dalziell EL,
398 Lewandrowski W, James JJ, Madsen MD (2017) Benefits of adopting seed-based
399 technologies for rehabilitation in the mining sector: a Pilbara perspective. *Australian*
400 *Journal of Botany* 65:646-660
- 401 Ferrenberg S, Faist AM, Howell A, and Reed SC (2017) Biocrusts enhance soil fertility and
402 *Bromus tectorum* growth, and interact with warming to influence germination. *Plant*
403 *and Soil* 429:77-90
- 404 Golos PJ, Dixon KW, Erickson TE (2016) Plant recruitment from the soil seed bank depends
405 on topsoil stockpile age, height, and storage history in an arid environment. *Restoration*
406 *Ecology* 24
- 407 Grigg AM, Veneklaas EJ, Lambers H (2008) Water relations and mineral nutrition of closely
408 related woody plant species on desert dunes and interdunes. *Australian Journal of*
409 *Botany* 56:27-43
- 410 Hashtroudi MS, Ghassempour A, Riahi H, Shariatmadari Z, Khanjir M (2013) Endogenous
411 auxins in plant growth-promoting Cyanobacteria—*Anabaena vaginicola* and *Nostoc*
412 *caldicola*. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 25:379-386
- 413 Havrilla CA, Barger NN (2018). Biocrusts and their disturbance mediate the recruitment of
414 native and exotic grasses from a hot desert ecosystem. *Ecosphere*, 9(7), e02361.

- 415 Havrilla CA, Chaudhary VB, Ferrenberg S, Antoninka AJ, Belnap J, Bowker MA, Eldridge DJ,
 416 Faist AM, Huber-Sannwald E, Leslie AD, Rodriguez-Caballero E, Zhang Y, Barger N
 417 (2019). Towards a predictive framework for biocrust mediation of plant performance: a
 418 meta-analysis. *Journal of Ecology* (in press). doi: 10.1111/1365-2745.13269
- 419 James JJ, Sheley RL, Erickson T, Rollins KS, Taylor MH, Dixon KW, Firm J (2013) A systems
 420 approach to restoring degraded drylands. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 50:730-739
- 421 Kneller T, Harris RJ, Bateman A, Muñoz-Rojas M (2018) Native-plant amendments and topsoil
 422 addition enhance soil function in post-mining arid grasslands. *Science of the Total*
 423 *Environment* 621:744-752
- 424 Lewandowski W, Erickson TE, Dixon KW, Stevens JC (2017) Increasing the germination
 425 envelope under water stress improves seedling emergence in two dominant grass
 426 species across different pulse rainfall events. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 54:997-1007
- 427 Madsen MD, Davies KW, Boyd CS, Kerby JD, Svejcar TJ (2016a) Emerging seed
 428 enhancement technologies for overcoming barriers to restoration. *Restoration Ecology*
 429 24: S77-S84.
- 430 Mahmood A, Turgay OC, Farooq M, Hayat R (2016) Seed biopriming with plant growth
 431 promoting rhizobacteria: a review. *FEMS microbiology ecology* 1:92
- 432 Mayence C, Stevens J, Courtney P, Dixon K (2017) Edaphic constraints on seed germination
 433 and emergence of three *Acacia* species for dryland restoration in Saudi Arabia. *Plant*
 434 *ecology* 218:55-66
- 435 Mazhar S, Cohen JD, Hasnain S (2013) Auxin producing non-heterocystous Cyanobacteria and
 436 their impact on the growth and endogenous auxin homeostasis of wheat. *Journal of basic*
 437 *microbiology* 53:996-1003
- 438 Mckenzie N, Van Leeuwen S, Pinder A (2009) Introduction to the Pilbara biodiversity survey,
 439 2002–2007. *Records of the Western Australian Museum, Supplement* 78:3-89
- 440 Merino-Martín L, Commander L, Mao Z, Stevens JC, Miller BP, Golos PJ, Mayence CE, Dixon
 441 K (2017) Overcoming topsoil deficits in restoration of semiarid lands: Designing
 442 hydrologically favourable soil covers for seedling emergence. *Ecological Engineering*
 443 105:102-117
- 444 Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (2005) *Ecosystems and Human Well-Being: Biodiversity*
 445 *Synthesis*, Published by World Resources Institute, Washington, DC
- 446 Mugnai G, Rossi F, Felde VJMNL, Colesie C, Büdel B, Peth S, Kaplan A, De Philippis R (2018)
 447 The potential of the cyanobacterium *Leptolyngbya ohadii* as inoculum for stabilizing
 448 bare sandy substrates. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*
- 449 Muñoz-Martín MÁ, Becerra-Absalón I, Perona E, Fernández-Valbuena L, Garcia-Pichel F, and
 450 Mateo P (2018) Cyanobacterial biocrust diversity in Mediterranean ecosystems along a
 451 latitudinal and climatic gradient. *New Phytologist*
- 452 Muñoz-Rojas M (2018) Soil quality indicators: a critical tool in ecosystem restoration. *Current*
 453 *Opinion in Environmental Science & Health*
- 454 Muñoz-Rojas M, Erickson TE, Martini DC, K. W. Dixon, Merritt DJ (2016) Climate and soil
 455 factors influencing seedling recruitment of plant species used for dryland restoration.
 456 *Soil* 2:287

- 457 Muñoz-Rojas M, Chilton A, Liyanage GS, Erickson TE, Merritt DJ, Neilan BA, Ooi MKJ
 458 (2018a) Effects of indigenous soil cyanobacteria on seed germination and seedling
 459 growth of arid species used in restoration. *Plant and Soil*
- 460 Muñoz-Rojas M, J.R. Románd, B. Roncero-Ramos, T.E. Erickson, D.J. Merritt, P. Águila-
 461 Carricondo, Y. Cantón (2018b) Cyanobacteria inoculation enhances carbon
 462 sequestration in soil substrates used in dryland restoration *Science of the Total*
 463 *Environment*
- 464 O'callaghan M (2016) Microbial inoculation of seed for improved crop performance: issues and
 465 opportunities. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* 100:5729-5746
- 466 Oldroyd GE, Dixon R (2014) Biotechnological solutions to the nitrogen problem. *Current*
 467 *opinion in biotechnology* 26:19-24
- 468 Park CH, Li XR, Zhao Y, Jia RL, Hur JS (2017) Rapid development of cyanobacterial crust in
 469 the field for combating desertification. *PLoS One* 12:e0179903
- 470 Pedrini S, Merritt DJ, Stevens J, Dixon K (2017) Seed coating: Science or marketing spin?
 471 *Trends in plant science* 22:106-116
- 472 Pereira P, Bogunovic I, Muñoz-Rojas M, Brevik EC (2017) Soil ecosystem services,
 473 sustainability, valuation and management. *Current Opinion in Environmental Science*
 474 *& Health*
- 475 R Core Team (2017) R: a language and environment for statistical computing. Vienna, Austria:
 476 R Foundation for Statistical Computing; 2017
- 477 Remigi P, Zhu J, Young JPW, Masson-Boivin C (2016) Symbiosis within symbiosis: evolving
 478 nitrogen-fixing legume symbionts. *Trends in microbiology* 24:63-75
- 479 Román JR, Roncero-Ramos B, Chamizo S, Rodríguez-Caballero E, Cantón Y (2018) Restoring
 480 soil functions by means of cyanobacteria inoculation: Importance of soil conditions and
 481 species selection. *Land Degradation & Development* 29:3184-3193
- 482 Roncero-Ramos B, Román JR, Rodríguez-Caballero ES, Chamizo S, Águila-Carricondo P,
 483 Mateo P, Cantón Y (2019) Assessing the influence of soil abiotic and biotic factors on
 484 *Nostoc commune* inoculation success *Plant Soil* (in press. doi: 10.1007/s11104-019-
 485 04239-y
- 486 Rossi F, Li H, Liu Y, De Philippis R (2017) Cyanobacterial inoculation (cyanobacterisation):
 487 Perspectives for the development of a standardized multifunctional technology for soil
 488 fertilization and desertification reversal. *Earth-Science Reviews* 171:28-43
- 489 Schwarz D, Orf I, Kopka J, Hagemann M (2013) Recent applications of metabolomics toward
 490 cyanobacteria. *Metabolites* 3:72-100
- 491 Shimura Y, Hirose Y, Misawa N, Osana Y, Katoh H, Yamaguchi H, Kawachi M (2015)
 492 Comparison of the terrestrial cyanobacterium *Leptolyngbya sp.* NIES-2104 and the
 493 freshwater *Leptolyngbya boryana* PCC 6306 genomes. *DNA Research* 22:403-412
- 494 Singh JS, Kumar A, Rai AN, Singh DP (2016) Cyanobacteria: a precious bio-resource in
 495 agriculture, ecosystem, and environmental sustainability. *Frontiers in microbiology*
 496 7:529
- 497 Song G, Li X, Hui R (2017) Effect of biological soil crusts on seed germination and growth of
 498 an exotic and two native plant species in an arid ecosystem. *PLoS One* 12:e0185839

- 499 Stavi I, and Lal R (2015) Achieving Zero Net Land Degradation: Challenges and opportunities.
500 Journal of Arid Environments 112:44-51
- 501 Swenson TL, Karaoz U, Swenson JM, Bowen BP, Northen TR (2018) Linking soil biology and
502 chemistry in biological soil crust using isolate exometabolomics. Nature
503 communications 9:19
- 504 Tedersoo L, Laanisto L, Rahimlou S, Toussaint A, Hallikma T, Pärtel M (2018) Global
505 database of plants with root-symbiotic nitrogen fixation: Nod DB. Journal of Vegetation
506 Science
- 507 Zaady E, Ben-David EA, Sher Y, Tzirkin R, Nejidat A (2010) Inferring biological soil crust
508 successional stage using combined PLFA, DGGE, physical and biophysiological
509 analyses. Soil Biology and Biochemistry 42:842-849
- 510 Zavřel T, Sinetova MA, Červený J (2015) Measurement of chlorophyll a and carotenoids
511 concentration in cyanobacteria. Bio-protocol 5: e1467.
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513 **Figures and tables**
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 517 **Figure 1.** Mean germination proportion of cyanobacteria bio-primed seeds (vs un-primed
 518 control seeds) over 16 d. Seeds were incubated in Petri dishes under a 16/8 h alternating
 519 temperature (28/20°C) and light:dark cycle. Levels of significance represent differences in
 520 germination proportion between bio-primed and non-primed seeds for each species.
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Figure 2. 10-day old seedling A) Shoot length (mm) and B) Radicle lengths (mm). Levels of significance represent differences in germination proportion between bio-primed and un-primed seeds for each species: (*) $P < 0.05$; (**) $P < 0.005$; (***) $P < 0.001$.

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Figure 3. Mean emergence proportion (\pm SE) of cyanobacteria bio-primed seeds (vs control) of *A. hilliana* (n = 40), *G. wickhamii* (n = 100) and *T. wiseana* (n = 100) sown in topsoil and mine waste soil. Different upper-case letters indicate significant differences between cyanobacteria treatments (non-primed vs bio-primed) and lower-case letters indicate significant differences between soil substrates (TS vs WS) for each cyanobacteria treatment (Tukey's comparisons, $P < 0.05$).

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545 **Figure 4.** A) TOC (%), B) TN (%), C) C:N and D) Soil microbial activity (CO₂-C ppm), in the soil
 546 before (TS Before, WS Before) and after (TS Control, TS Bio-primed, WS Control and WS Bio-primed)
 547 the experiment. Different upper-case letters indicate significant differences between cyanobacteria
 548 treatments (non-primed vs bio-primed) and lower-case letters indicate significant differences between
 549 soil substrates (TS vs WS) for each cyanobacteria treatment (Tukey's comparisons, $P < 0.05$).

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552 **Table 1.** Mean Shoot length¹ (mm) and biomass² (g) of *A. hilliana*, *G. wickhamii* and *T. wiseana*
553 measured 5, 6, 8 and 20 weeks after seeds were sown in topsoil (TS) and mine waste soil (WS) (Mean
554 \pm SE). Lowercase letters indicate significant differences between treatments (Tukey's comparisons, $P <$
555 0.05). Different upper-case letters indicate significant differences between cyanobacteria treatments
556 (non-primed vs bio-primed) and lower-case letters indicate significant differences between soil
557 substrates (TS vs WS) for each cyanobacteria treatment (Tukey's comparisons, $P <$ 0.05).
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Plant species	Times since sown (weeks)	Treatments			
		TS		WS	
		Control	Bio-primed	Control	Bio-primed
<i>A. hilliana</i>	5 ¹	40.7 \pm 1.4 ^{Aa}	38.8 \pm 1.4 ^{Aa}	38.7 \pm 1.5 ^{Aa}	37.4 \pm 1.4 ^{Aa}
	6 ¹	40.9 \pm 1.2 ^{Aa}	38.3 \pm 1.5 ^{Aa}	37.4 \pm 1.6 ^{Aa}	37.6 \pm 1.2 ^{Aa}
	8 ¹	45.2 \pm 1.5 ^{Aa}	41.8 \pm 1.5 ^{Aa}	42.9 \pm 1.4 ^{Aa}	43.5 \pm 1.3 ^{Aa}
	20 ¹	72.8 \pm 6.5 ^{Ba}	100.0 \pm 13.8 ^{Aa}	55.4 \pm 3.2 ^{Bb}	72.9 \pm 5.4 ^{Ab}
	20 ²	0.95 \pm 0.30 ^{Aa}	1.82 \pm 0.90 ^{Aa}	0.4 \pm 0.05 ^{Bb}	1.11 \pm 0.30 ^{Aa}
<i>G. wickhamii</i>	5 ¹	39.1 \pm 2.1 ^{Aa}	36.1 \pm 1.8 ^{Aa}	37.1 \pm 2.1 ^{Aa}	29.0 \pm 3.0 ^{Bb}
	6 ¹	37.7 \pm 1.9 ^{Aa}	33.9 \pm 1.7 ^{Ba}	38.4 \pm 2.0 ^{Aa}	31.4 \pm 3.2 ^{Ba}
	8 ¹	41.2 \pm 1.89 ^{Ab}	38.3 \pm 1.8 ^{Aa}	49.7 \pm 2.4 ^{Aa}	36.6 \pm 2.7 ^{Ba}
	20 ¹	60.3 \pm 4.0 ^{Ab}	57.6 \pm 2.4 ^{Ab}	122.5 \pm 10.7 ^{Aa}	116.3 \pm 11.3 ^{Aa}
	20 ²	0.88 \pm 0.30 ^{Ab}	0.82 \pm 0.20 ^{Ab}	8.87 \pm 0.05 ^{Aa}	6.11 \pm 1.4 ^{Ba}
<i>T. wiseana</i>	5 ¹	50.8 \pm 2.9 ^{Aa}	52.6 \pm 3.1 ^{Aa}	32.7 \pm 2.9 ^{Ab}	30.0 \pm 3.6 ^{Ab}
	6 ¹	68.9 \pm 5.5 ^{Aa}	60.9 \pm 4.7 ^{Aa}	31.9 \pm 3.5 ^{Ab}	33.9 \pm 5.2 ^{Ab}
	8 ¹	94.5 \pm 5.9 ^{Aa}	88.3 \pm 4.3 ^{Aa}	37.2 \pm 3.3 ^{Ab}	35.1 \pm 4.5 ^{Ab}
	20 ¹	138.3 \pm 9.4 ^{Ba}	179.0 \pm 5.2 ^{Aa}	39.1 \pm 3.7 ^{Ab}	33.4 \pm 3.1 ^{Ab}
	20 ²	10.80 \pm 2.70 ^{Aa}	10.67 \pm 1.10 ^{Aa}	9.30 \pm 2.60 ^{Aa}	7.30 \pm 1.60 ^{Aa}

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562 **Supplementary Information**

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564 **Table S1.** List of plant species native to the Pilbara, Western Australia and their species-specific treatment to break dormancy.

Family	Species	Seed Dormancy Class	Seed Pre-treatment
Fabaceae	<i>Acacia hilliona</i>	Physical	2 mins at 95 °C
Fabaceae	<i>Acacia inaequilatera</i>	Physical	2 mins at 95 °C
Myrtaceae	<i>Eucalyptus gamophylla</i>	Non-dormant	-
Proteaceae	<i>Grevillea wickhamii</i>	Non-dormant	-
Fabaceae	<i>Indigofera monophylla</i>	Physical	1-2 mins at 70 – 90 °C
Fabaceae	<i>Senna notabilis</i>	Physical	1 min at 70 – 90 °C
Poaceae	<i>Triodia wiseana</i>	Physiological	Remove floret structures covering seeds

565 Table adapted from (Erickson et al. 2016)

566 **Table S2.** Characteristics of the cyanobacteria cultures forming the seed-bioprimer inoculant.

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Cyanobacteria species	Culture		Dry biomass	
	Chlorophyll <i>a</i> (µg· ml ⁻¹)	Carotenoid (µg· ml ⁻¹)	Chlorophyll <i>a</i> (µg· ml ⁻¹)	Carotenoid (µg· ml ⁻¹)
<i>Leptolyngbia</i> sp.	0.53±0.05	0.26±0.03	26.73±2.70	12.87±1.57
<i>Microcoleus</i> sp.	0.35±0.14	0.28±0.18	8.84±3.44	7.11±4.53
<i>Nostoc</i> sp.	1.32±0.18	0.38±0.12	22.05±3.02	6.35±1.94
<i>Scytonema</i> sp.	0.45±0.01	0.63±0.44	8.99±0.13	12.55±8.80

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